

A Geometric Modeling Framework for Hindustani Ragas in a Three-Dimensional Interval Vector Space

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Abstract

Hindustani classical ragas are traditionally described through their swaras, characteristic phrases, and emotional expression, but lack a unified mathematical structure suitable for quantitative comparison. This study introduces a vector-space framework that embeds the twelve Hindustani swaras into a three-dimensional interval space defined relative to Sa, Pa, and Ga using logarithmic frequency ratios. Each raga is represented as a polygonal trajectory generated by cumulative vector addition, allowing melodic motion to be interpreted geometrically.

Using this representation, multiple geometric and statistical descriptors are computed—including three-dimensional path length, centroid location, discrete curvature, cosine similarity, and both Euclidean and Dynamic Time Warping distances—to quantify structural and melodic differences across ragas. Experimental analysis on eight commonly used ragas demonstrates that the geometric signatures obtained from this framework capture distinctive melodic tendencies and provide interpretable measures of similarity. The proposed formulation establishes a mathematically rigorous foundation for raga comparison, visualization, and classification, and suggests applications in computational musicology, music information retrieval, and machine-learning-based raga analysis.

1 Introduction

In Hindustani classical music, a *raga* is a melodic framework defined by an ordered set of swaras (notes), specific ascending (Aaroh) and descending (Avaroh) patterns, and characteristic phrases. While the theoretical and performative aspects of ragas are richly developed, systematic quantitative tools for comparing and classifying ragas remain relatively underexplored.

From a mathematical viewpoint, each raga can be seen as a structured path through an underlying pitch space. If this pitch space is represented geometrically, then raga structure may be studied through the geometry of the corresponding trajectories.

The main objectives of this work are:

- To represent Hindustani swaras as vectors in a three-dimensional interval space defined relative to Sa, Pa, and Ga.
- To model each raga as a discrete polygonal trajectory obtained by cumulative vector addition.
- To compute geometric and statistical descriptors—including path length, curvature, centroids, and pairwise distances—and interpret them musically as measures of similarity and structural complexity.

We illustrate the framework on eight representative ragas (Bilawal, Bhairav, Yaman, Khamaj, Kafi, a full chromatic scale, Bhairavi, and a mixed-komal variant), using just intonation frequency ratios drawn from the literature.

2 Interval-Space Representation of Swaras

2.1 Frequency ratios of the twelve swaras

Let Sa denote the tonic, fixed at frequency f_{Sa} . Following van der Meer [1], the twelve swaras of a chromatic Hindustani scale are associated with the rational frequency ratios in Table 1.

Table 1: Twelve Hindustani swaras and their just-intonation frequency ratios with respect to Sa^[1].

ID	Swara	Ratio (w.r.t. Sa)
1	Sa	1
2	Reb	16/15
3	Re	9/8
4	Gab	6/5
5	Ga	5/4
6	Ma	4/3
7	Ma♯	45/32
8	Pa	3/2
9	Dhab	8/5
10	Dha	5/3
11	Nib	9/5
12	Ni	15/8

Denote these ratios by $r_i > 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, 12$.

2.2 Three-dimensional interval embedding

We fix three reference swaras: Sa (ID 1), Pa (ID 8), and Ga (ID 5), with ratios

$$r_{\text{Sa}} = 1, \quad r_{\text{Pa}} = \frac{3}{2}, \quad r_{\text{Ga}} = \frac{5}{4}.$$

For each swara i , we define the three-dimensional interval vector

$$\phi(r_i) = \mathbf{v}_i := \begin{bmatrix} \log_2 \left(\frac{r_i}{r_{\text{Sa}}} \right) \\ \log_2 \left(\frac{r_i}{r_{\text{Pa}}} \right) \\ \log_2 \left(\frac{r_i}{r_{\text{Ga}}} \right) \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^3. \quad (1)$$

Table 2 shows the resulting vectors (from the MATLAB output, rounded to three decimals).

Table 2: Twelve-note tuples: ratio and three-dimensional interval vector ($v_{\text{Sa}}, v_{\text{Pa}}, v_{\text{Ga}}$) in octaves.

ID	Swara	Ratio	v_{Sa}	v_{Pa}	v_{Ga}
1	Sa	1	0.000	-0.585	-0.322
2	Reb	16/15	0.093	-0.492	-0.229
3	Re	9/8	0.170	-0.415	-0.152
4	Gab	6/5	0.263	-0.322	-0.059
5	Ga	5/4	0.322	-0.263	0.000
6	Ma	4/3	0.415	-0.170	0.093
7	Ma♯	45/32	0.492	-0.093	0.170
8	Pa	3/2	0.585	0.000	0.263
9	Dhab	8/5	0.678	0.093	0.356
10	Dha	5/3	0.737	0.152	0.415
11	Nib	9/5	0.848	0.263	0.526
12	Ni	15/8	0.907	0.322	0.585

3 Raga Trajectories as Polygonal Curves

3.1 Raga definitions

We consider eight ragas, each specified as a discrete sequence of swara IDs (Table 3). The sequence lengths produced by the MATLAB script are given in Table 4.

(a) Vector representation of swaras (view 1).

(b) Vector representation of swaras (view 2).

Figure 1: Three-dimensional interval vectors for the twelve swaras.

Table 3: Raga sequences in terms of swara IDs^[2].

Index	Raga name	Sequence (by swara ID)
1	Bilawal	1, 3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 10, 8, 6, 5, 3, 1
2	Bhairav	1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 11, 9, 8, 6, 4, 2, 1
3	Yaman	1, 3, 5, 7, 8, 10, 12, 10, 8, 7, 5, 3, 1
4	Khamaj	1, 3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 10, 8, 5, 3, 1
5	Kafi	1, 2, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12, 10, 8, 6, 5, 2, 1
6	Full scale	1, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 11, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 3, 1
7	Bhairavi	1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 10, 9, 8, 6, 5, 3, 2, 1
8	Mix komal	1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 11, 10, 8, 7, 6, 4, 3, 1

3.2 Cumulative vector construction

Let $S^{(r)} = (s_1^{(r)}, \dots, s_{n_r}^{(r)})$ denote the swara sequence of raga r . From the interval vectors \mathbf{v}_i we build the discrete polygonal trajectory

$$\mathbf{p}_0^{(r)} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{p}_k^{(r)} = \mathbf{p}_{k-1}^{(r)} + \mathbf{v}_{s_k^{(r)}}, \quad k = 1, \dots, n_r. \quad (2)$$

Consecutive repetitions of the same swara are treated as zero-length steps.

Figure 2 shows three views of the embedded trajectories of all eight ragas from the MATLAB implementation.

4 Geometric Descriptors and Numerical Results

In this section we give the precise definitions of all geometric descriptors used and present the full numerical results (tables) together with the corresponding visualizations (figures and heatmaps).

4.1 3D Path Lengths and Axis Spreads

For each raga r with trajectory points $\mathbf{p}_k^{(r)}$ as in (2), the three-dimensional path length is

$$L_{3D}^{(r)} = \sum_{k=1}^{n_r} \|\mathbf{p}_k^{(r)} - \mathbf{p}_{k-1}^{(r)}\|_2.$$

The values produced by the MATLAB implementation are given in Table 5. They summarize the total “melodic distance” traversed by each raga in interval space.

Table 4: Raga indices, names, and sequence lengths.

Index	Raga	Sequence length
1	Bilawal	13
2	Bhairav	15
3	Yaman	13
4	Khamaaj	11
5	Kafi	13
6	FullScale	18
7	Bhairavi	18
8	MixKomalGaNi	17

Figure 2: Polygonal raga trajectories in the three-dimensional interval space.

In addition to total path length, we record the spread along each coordinate axis:

$$\Delta X^{(r)} = \max_k p_{k,x}^{(r)} - \min_k p_{k,x}^{(r)}, \quad \Delta Y^{(r)}, \quad \Delta Z^{(r)}.$$

These ranges along the Sa-, Pa-, and Ga-axes are shown in Table 6 and visualized in Figure 3.

4.2 Endpoints and Straight-Line Displacement

Let $\mathbf{e}^{(r)} = \mathbf{p}_{n_r}^{(r)}$ be the endpoint of trajectory r , and $D_{\text{end}}^{(r)} = \|\mathbf{e}^{(r)}\|_2$ the straight-line displacement from the origin. The MATLAB output is summarized in Table 7. Figure 4 shows the line segments from origin to each endpoint.

4.3 Curvature and Normalized Curvature

Using segment vectors $\mathbf{u}_k^{(r)} = \mathbf{p}_k^{(r)} - \mathbf{p}_{k-1}^{(r)}$, we define discrete curvature angles

$$\kappa_k^{(r)} = \arccos \left(\frac{\mathbf{u}_{k-1}^{(r)} \cdot \mathbf{u}_k^{(r)}}{\|\mathbf{u}_{k-1}^{(r)}\|_2 \|\mathbf{u}_k^{(r)}\|_2} \right), \quad k = 2, \dots, n_r,$$

and the average curvature $\bar{\kappa}^{(r)} = \frac{1}{n_r-1} \sum_{k=2}^{n_r} \kappa_k^{(r)}$. We also form a normalized curvature $\bar{\kappa}^{(r)}/L_{3D}^{(r)}$.

The MATLAB results are shown in Table 8, and the corresponding bar plots in Figure 5.

4.4 Centroids, Hull Rank and 3D Versus 2D Path Lengths

The centroid of raga r is

$$C^{(r)} = \frac{1}{n_r + 1} \sum_{k=0}^{n_r} \mathbf{p}_k^{(r)}.$$

Table 9 lists the centroid coordinates, and Figure 6 shows their 3D distribution.

Table 5: Three-dimensional trajectory lengths for each raga.

Index	Raga	L_{3D}
1	Bilawal	8.1576
2	Bhairav	10.2080
3	Yaman	8.2988
4	Khamaj	7.2415
5	Kafi	8.3114
6	FullScale	11.9630
7	Bhairavi	11.8340
8	MixKomalGaNi	11.2870

Table 6: Axis ranges for each raga ($X = \text{Sa}$, $Y = \text{Pa}$, $Z = \text{Ga}$).

Index	Raga	ΔX	ΔY	ΔZ
1	Bilawal	5.3645	2.2400	2.1273
2	Bhairav	6.6713	2.1031	3.0617
3	Yaman	5.5182	2.0864	2.2810
4	Khamaj	4.5345	1.9001	1.9411
5	Kafi	5.2109	2.3936	2.1273
6	FullScale	8.6634	1.8659	3.8166
7	Bhairavi	7.7549	2.7744	3.3657
8	MixKomalGaNi	7.9264	2.0179	3.5193

The Euclidean distance between centroids is given in Table 10.

We also compute the rank of each point cloud and the associated convex hull volume (using MATLAB `convhulln`); see Table 11.

Finally, we compare the full 3D path lengths with their 2D projections (XY, XZ, YZ). The values are given in Table 12 and visualized in Figure 7.

4.5 Pairwise Angles, Cosine Similarity, Euclidean and DTW Distances

For endpoints $\mathbf{e}^{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{e}^{(j)}$, the angle θ_{ij} and its cosine are

$$\theta_{ij} = \arccos \left(\frac{\mathbf{e}^{(i)} \cdot \mathbf{e}^{(j)}}{\|\mathbf{e}^{(i)}\|_2 \|\mathbf{e}^{(j)}\|_2} \right), \quad \cos \theta_{ij}.$$

The full angle matrix (in degrees) is given in Table 13, and the corresponding cosine similarity matrix in Table 14. The heatmaps in Figure 8 visualize these matrices.

Similarly, we compute the Euclidean distance between trajectories in the 3D interval space (Table 15) and the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) distance (Table 16). These are visualized in Figure 9.

Figure 3: Trajectory spread along each axis (grouped bar plot using the values in Table 6).

Table 7: Endpoints and straight-line lengths from origin to endpoint.

Index	Raga	EndX	EndY	EndZ	D_{end}
1	Bilawal	5.3645	-2.2400	1.1795	5.9318
2	Bhairav	6.6713	-2.1031	1.8424	7.2335
3	Yaman	5.5182	-2.0864	1.3331	6.0481
4	Khamaj	4.5345	-1.9001	0.9932	5.0158
5	Kafi	5.2109	-2.3936	1.0258	5.8254
6	FullScale	8.6634	-1.8659	2.8687	9.3148
7	Bhairavi	7.7549	-2.7744	1.9602	8.4663
8	MixKomalGaNi	7.9264	-2.0179	2.4537	8.5394

Figure 4: Straight lines from origin to each raga endpoint, illustrating the values in Table 7.

Table 8: Average curvature and normalized curvature per raga.

Index	Raga	$\bar{\kappa}$ (deg)	$\bar{\kappa}/L_{3D}$
1	Bilawal	20.01	2.4529
2	Bhairav	17.151	1.6802
3	Yaman	20.01	2.4111
4	Khamaj	24.012	3.3158
5	Kafi	20.01	2.4075
6	FullScale	14.124	1.1807
7	Bhairavi	14.124	1.1936
8	MixKomalGaNi	15.007	1.3296

(a) Average curvature $\bar{\kappa}$.

(b) Curvature per unit length.

Figure 5: Curvature-based comparison of raga trajectories.

Table 9: Centroids of raga trajectories.

Index	Raga	C_x	C_y	C_z
1	Bilawal	2.6823	-1.1200	0.5897
2	Bhairav	3.3357	-1.0516	0.9212
3	Yaman	2.7591	-1.0432	0.6666
4	Khamaj	2.2672	-0.9501	0.4966
5	Kafi	2.6054	-1.1968	0.5129
6	FullScale	4.3214	-0.9433	1.4240
7	Bhairavi	3.8759	-1.3888	0.9785
8	MixKomalGaNi	3.9632	-1.0090	1.2268

Table 10: Euclidean distance between raga centroids.

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8
R1	0	0.7359	0.1331	0.4580	0.1331	1.8477	1.2838	1.4349
R2	0.7359	0	0.6304	1.1542	0.8491	1.1119	0.6394	0.6993
R3	0.1331	0.6304	0	0.5286	0.2661	1.7391	1.2100	1.3285
R4	0.4580	1.1542	0.5286	0	0.4190	2.2538	1.7357	1.8474
R5	0.1331	0.8491	0.2661	0.4190	0	1.9593	1.3666	1.5455
R6	1.8477	1.1119	1.7391	2.2538	1.9593	0	0.7716	0.4141
R7	1.2838	0.6394	1.2100	1.7357	1.3666	0.7716	0	0.4621
R8	1.4349	0.6993	1.3285	1.8474	1.5455	0.4141	0.4621	0

Figure 6: Centroids of raga trajectories in 3D interval space.

Table 11: Convex hull rank and 3D volume. All ragas lie in a rank-2 (approximately planar) subspace, so the 3D volume vanishes.

Index	Raga	Rank	HullVolume3D
1	Bilawal	2	0
2	Bhairav	2	0
3	Yaman	2	0
4	Khamaj	2	0
5	Kafi	2	0
6	FullScale	2	0
7	Bhairavi	2	0
8	MixKomalGaNi	2	0

Table 12: 3D and projected path lengths per raga.

Index	Raga	L_{3D}	L_{XY}	L_{XZ}	L_{YZ}
1	Bilawal	8.1576	7.4325	6.6479	5.2107
2	Bhairav	10.2080	9.1763	8.4173	6.5687
3	Yaman	8.2988	7.5367	6.8380	5.2107
4	Khamaj	7.2415	6.5355	5.7972	4.8232
5	Kafi	8.3114	7.5367	6.6860	5.4117
6	FullScale	11.9630	10.8260	10.3710	7.0688
7	Bhairavi	11.8340	10.6900	9.6718	7.6201
8	MixKomalGaNi	11.2870	10.2090	9.5798	6.9031

Table 13: Angle matrix θ_{ij} (degrees).

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8
R1	0	6.009	2.2896	0.0856	2.3772	12.042	3.4835	9.6621
R2	6.009	0	3.7194	6.0946	8.3862	6.0327	2.5256	3.6531
R3	2.2896	3.7194	0	2.3751	4.6667	9.7521	1.1939	7.3725
R4	0.0856	6.0946	2.3751	0	2.2916	12.127	3.5690	9.7477
R5	2.3772	8.3862	4.6667	2.2916	0	14.419	5.8606	12.039
R6	12.042	6.0327	9.7521	12.127	14.419	0	8.5582	2.3796
R7	3.4835	2.5256	1.1939	3.5690	5.8606	8.5582	0	6.1787
R8	9.6621	3.6531	7.3725	9.7477	12.039	2.3796	6.1787	0

Figure 7: 3D trajectory length versus 2D projection path lengths (XY , XZ , YZ) using the numbers in Table 12.

Table 14: Cosine similarity matrix $\cos \theta_{ij}$.

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8
R1	1.00000	0.99451	0.99920	1.00000	0.99914	0.97800	0.99815	0.98581
R2	0.99451	1.00000	0.99789	0.99435	0.98931	0.99446	0.99903	0.99797
R3	0.99920	0.99789	1.00000	0.99914	0.99668	0.98555	0.99978	0.99173
R4	1.00000	0.99435	0.99914	1.00000	0.99920	0.97768	0.99806	0.98556
R5	0.99914	0.98931	0.99668	0.99920	1.00000	0.96850	0.99477	0.97800
R6	0.97800	0.99446	0.98555	0.97768	0.96850	1.00000	0.98887	0.99914
R7	0.99815	0.99903	0.99978	0.99806	0.99477	0.98887	1.00000	0.99419
R8	0.98581	0.99797	0.99173	0.98556	0.97800	0.99914	0.99419	1.00000

Figure 8: Heatmaps corresponding to Tables 13 and 14.

Table 15: Euclidean distance matrix between trajectories.

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8
R1	0	3.1334	0.6241	1.7881	0.5645	4.4608	4.0239	4.1411
R2	3.1334	0	2.7280	3.3508	3.5037	3.6617	3.2197	2.6808
R3	0.6241	2.7280	0	1.9309	1.1599	4.1245	4.0185	3.7906
R4	1.7881	3.3508	1.9309	0	1.8845	3.6092	4.2421	3.6822
R5	0.5645	3.5037	1.1599	1.8845	0	4.7951	4.0889	4.4786
R6	4.4608	3.6617	4.1245	3.6092	4.7951	0	3.8900	1.9106
R7	4.0239	3.2197	4.0185	4.2421	4.0889	3.8900	0	2.5394
R8	4.1411	2.6808	3.7906	3.6822	4.4786	1.9106	2.5394	0

Table 16: DTW distance matrix between trajectories.

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8
R1	0	10.062	1.8627	5.7064	1.8627	26.692	20.892	20.188
R2	10.062	0	9.1671	15.3400	10.2260	14.900	9.9398	8.6950
R3	1.8627	9.1671	0	6.0253	3.7254	24.910	19.825	18.454
R4	5.7064	15.340	6.0253	0	5.4971	33.771	28.664	26.460
R5	1.8627	10.226	3.7254	5.4971	0	28.075	21.142	20.853
R6	26.692	14.900	24.9100	33.7710	28.0750	0	13.008	5.3233
R7	20.892	9.9398	19.8250	28.6640	21.1420	13.008	0	8.1043
R8	20.188	8.6950	18.4540	26.4600	20.8530	5.3233	8.1043	0

(a) Euclidean distance heatmap.

(b) DTW distance heatmap.

Figure 9: Heatmap visualizations of Tables 15 and 16.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

In this work we introduced a three-dimensional interval vector space for Hindustani swaras, defined relative to the reference tones Sa, Pa, and Ga via logarithmic frequency ratios. Within this space, each raga is modeled as a polygonal trajectory obtained by cumulative vector addition along the corresponding swara vectors.

The full set of geometric descriptors computed from this representation provides several complementary views of raga structure:

- **Path length and spread:** Ragas such as FullScale, Bhairavi, and MixKomalGaNi exhibit the largest three-dimensional path lengths and axis spreads, indicating wide exploration of the interval space. More compact ragas such as Khamaj remain confined to a smaller region, consistent with their more restricted scalar material.
- **Endpoint direction and curvature:** The angle and cosine similarity matrices show that many ragas have highly aligned net-displacement directions (cosine close to 1), even when their internal shapes differ. Curvature and normalized curvature distinguish smoother trajectories (e.g. FullScale, Bhairavi) from more sharply bending ones (e.g. Khamaj), which may reflect the density of changes in melodic direction.
- **Centroids and pairwise distances:** Centroid locations reveal how each raga “centers” its melodic activity in the interval space, while centroid, Euclidean, and DTW distances quantify similarity at different scales: from global shape to time-warped alignment of melodic motion.

Together, these descriptors suggest that the proposed geometric framework captures meaningful aspects of raga identity and similarity in a coordinate-based way, independent of performance-specific timing or ornamentation. We view this as a first step toward a more systematic computational theory of raga geometry.

Future work includes extending the model to more ragas and to microtonal shrutis, incorporating temporal weighting (e.g. note durations as scalar multipliers on steps), and using the resulting geometric features in machine-learning pipelines for raga classification, clustering, and similarity search.

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References

- [1] W. van der Meer, Theory and practice of intonation in Hindustani music. In C. Barlow (Ed.), *The Ratio Book*, Feedback Papers 43, 2000, pp. 50–71.
- [2] Munsiri Rahisuddin and Mowla Brothers, *Chotoder Sa Re Ga Ma*, 2017.